

Magnesium Polysulfides: Synthesis, Disproportionation, and Impedance Response in Symmetrical Carbon Electrode Cells

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Magnesium polysulfides have a key role during the redox reaction in magnesium-sulfur batteries. However, kinetics of the Mg polysulfide disproportionation, transport, and solubility in electrolytes are rarely studied. To fill this gap, we here report the synthesis of different chain-length Mg polysulfides and their characterization with ¹H NMR, ATR-IR, and XANES spectroscopies. The tendency of polysulfides to disproportionate in solutions is confirmed with UV/Vis spectroscopy. To probe their reactivity and diffusivity, impedance spectroscopy is performed

in symmetrical cells consisting of two planar glassy carbon or porous carbon electrodes containing Mg polysulfide catholyte. Several transport-reaction parameters are obtained, such as exchange current densities, chemical diffusion coefficients, transference numbers of polysulfides, and conductivities. Moreover, we show that the solubility of Mg polysulfides in Mg(TFSI)₂, MgCl₂ ether-based electrolyte is affected at rather moderate concentration of polysulfides, thereby having an impact on the cell performance.

1. Introduction

Society demands sustainable solutions to reduce the strain on the environment while meeting growing energy demands. In the last decades, lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries have revolutionized portable electronics and started an electromobility revolution by storing three times more the energy by volume and mass than competing systems.^[1–3] However, the ever increasing demand for new batteries will increase the cost of rare and scarce resources, like lithium, nickel, and cobalt, which might even induce geopolitical tensions. To overcome these problems, one needs to focus on the more earth-abundant elements for anode and cathode materials.

Magnesium and sulfur are both earth-abundant elements, whose combination in a battery would allow to reach future energy densities up to 320–440 Wh kg⁻¹ and 600–780 Wh l⁻¹.^[4,5] Magnesium-sulfur (Mg–S) battery is an attractive, promising, and low-cost future battery technology, which was first demonstrated by Muldoon and co-workers in 2011.^[6] In the past years extensive studies have been focused on the working principles of Mg–S battery. The basic sulfur conversion reaction concept^[7–13] is similar to the Li–S battery, however the Mg–S system^[5,14,15] has also different involved reactions.

Typically, Mg–S battery in the ether-based electrolytes exhibits two plateaus, a high and a low voltage one, representing the formation of long and short chain Mg polysulfides, respectively. The final discharge product is MgS, which precipitates as an amorphous film on the cathode surface.^[13] Therefore, similar problems as known from the Li–S battery plague also Mg–S battery, i.e. self-discharge, a low cycle life due to fast capacity fade, the shuttle effect, and constraints stemming from polysulfide depletion in the process of MgS precipitation.^[9,16,17] A lot of effort has been devoted to development of weakly coordinated magnesium salts and new non-nucleophilic electrolyte concepts for Mg–S battery to overcome the low cycle lifetime.^[7,9,18,19] However, there are only few reports on the kinetics of the Mg polysulfide disproportionation,^[14,20] transport and solubility in the electrolytes. In order to get this information, one needs to synthesize and characterize reliable Mg polysulfide standards and evaluate their basic electrochemical properties.

In this work we report a successful synthesis of different chain length Mg polysulfides and their characterization with ¹H NMR, ATR-IR spectroscopy, and sulfur K-edge X-ray absorption near edge spectroscopy (XANES) measurements. *In situ* UV-vis spectroscopy is used to monitor the spontaneous Mg polysulfide degree of disproportionation. Moreover, impedance

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spectroscopy is employed to study the reaction kinetics in symmetrical cells with symmetrical planar or porous electrodes.

2. Results and Discussion

Mg polysulfides of different chain lengths were synthesized according to the literature.^[20,21] Specifically, the synthesis (Figure 1a) was based on the reduction of elemental sulfur in a strong donor solvent such as *N*-methylimidazole (*N*-Melm). As can be seen from the ATR-IR spectra of the prepared Mg polysulfides (Figure 1b), *N*-Melm peaks are present, suggesting a formation of Mg polysulfide *N*-Melm complex. According to the literature,^[21] 6 *N*-Melm molecules are coordinated around the Mg²⁺ cation. A shift of protons at the position 4 and 6 of the coordinated *N*-Melm is observed (Figure S1) as detected by the ¹H NMR. This proton shift indicates that the Mg²⁺ cation is coordinated with the nitrogen of the donor *N*-Melm ligand at the position 5, forming a [Mg(*N*-Melm)₆]²⁺ complex. The stability of the prepared magnesium polysulfides complexes arises from the effect of basic *N*-donor ligand. ATR-IR spectra (Figure 1b, c) show a decrease in sulfur chain length which results in a redshift of the peak belonging to the –S–S– stretching vibration,^[22] going from [Mg(*N*-Melm)₆]₈S₈ at 507 cm⁻¹ and [Mg(*N*-Melm)₆]₆S₆ at 505 cm⁻¹ to [Mg(*N*-Melm)₆]₄S₄ at 497 cm⁻¹. To unambiguously confirm the formation of Mg polysulfides, sulfur K-edge XANES was performed (Figure 1d). The XANES spectra of the Mg polysulfides show two characteristic peaks, a pre-peak for the terminal S²⁻ at 2470.2 eV and a main sulfur peak at 2472 eV.^[13] Comparing the intensities of the pre-peak and the main peak from Figure 1d, it is possible to observe the characteristic trend for polysulfides, i.e. with the decrease of the polysulfide chain length the ratio between the intensity of the pre-peak and the intensity of the main peak increases.^[13,23]

The typical Mg–S cell discharge/charge galvanostatic curve is presented in Figure S2. The first half of the galvanostatic

curve represents the discharge of the cell and the second half the charge. The higher voltage plateau at approx. 1.3 V vs Mg/Mg²⁺ corresponds to the conversion of solid sulfur into soluble magnesium polysulfides and the lower plateau around 1 V vs Mg/Mg²⁺ to the reduction of magnesium polysulfides into the insoluble magnesium sulfide.^[13] The charge proceeds in the opposite direction via a quasi-single plateau. In order to evaluate the kinetics of the Mg polysulfide disproportionation, diffusivity, and reactivity, we prepared catholytes by dissolving Mg polysulfides in a 0.4 M Mg(TFSI)₂ 0.4 M MgCl₂ TEGDME:DOL 1:1 (v:v) electrolyte. The polysulfide concentration was arbitrarily chosen to correspond to the electrolyte loading of 200 μL per mg of sulfur in the cathode, which resulted in a 0.018 M MgS₈ solution. The MgS₆ and MgS₄ solutions were prepared of equal concentration. It is known that lithium polysulfides are prone to disproportionate and typically form a mixture of polysulfides with different chain lengths when dissolved in the electrolyte.^[24,25] Therefore, we first determined whether the same process also prevailed in the electrolyte with dissolved magnesium polysulfides. The disproportionation reactions of polysulfides were studied by UV-vis spectroscopy. With this technique, the spectra of the catholyte within glass fiber separator (packed in a pouch cell with a quartz glass window) were continuously measured over the period of 70 hours. Figure 2 shows the changes in reflectance for MgS₄ (top row) and MgS₆ catholytes (bottom row). Although the differences were too small to be visually observed (Figures S3, S4), small changes are evident from the UV-vis spectra, confirming disproportionation reactions in solutions of magnesium polysulfides. Thus, the concentrations provided at the beginning of this study should be considered nominal and it should always be considered that the solutions employed are a complex mixture of polysulfides of different chain lengths.

Reflectance values for the wavelength where the change was most substantial (shown with an arrow) were extracted from the spectra. (1-R)² (2R)⁻¹ values, which are linearly related

Figure 1. Synthesis and characterization of magnesium polysulfides: a) synthesis scheme for preparation of MgS_x from elemental Mg and S; b) IR spectra of the *N*-Melm solvent and different Mg polysulfides; c) magnification of the 560–400 cm⁻¹ region of the IR spectra showing –S–S– stretching vibration; d) sulfur K-edge XANES measurements comparing elemental sulfur and synthesized magnesium polysulfides.

Figure 2. UV/Vis spectroscopy measurements of 0.018 M magnesium polysulfide catholytes within 70 hours after solution preparation. a) UV/Vis spectra change and b) reflectance change at 520 nm (given as $(1-R)^2/(2R)^{-1}$, which is linearly correlated with concentration) for MgS_4 catholyte. c, d) UV/Vis spectra change and reflectance at 680 nm for MgS_6 catholyte, respectively.

to the concentration of species through the Kubelka-Munk equation,^[26] are shown in Figure 2b and d. As seen from the extracted reflectance values, the two tested solutions have substantially different degree of conversion. MgS_6 solution seems to be rather stable, with a small decrease in the concentration of species absorbing light at 680 nm, while MgS_4 solution shows a larger change with an increase in the concentration of species absorbing light at 520 nm and a slight increase of reflectance at the upper wavelength limit. Both the increase and decrease in the concentration of detected species due to disproportionation was already shown to be possible in lithium polysulfide solutions.^[24,26]

Since the disproportionation phenomenon is complex, we wish to keep our analysis at a qualitative level, since determination of the conversion reaction mechanism will not provide exact results. The UV-vis spectroscopy experiment provides a proof that the degree of disproportionation is dependent on the starting oxidation state, although we cannot say for certain that the MgS_6 polysulfide is always the most stable when in solution. Namely, since polysulfides of different chain length are soluble to a different degree, we would also expect the conversion to be different when changing the concentration of the species. In summary, this experiment therefore showed that magnesium polysulfides undergo disproportionation reactions. The rate of disproportionation is dependent upon the exact composition of the catholyte. Moreover, the catholyte changes can be minimal or of a high degree. In parallel with the research on the Li-S batteries and limited information available for the Mg-S system, disproportionation reactions heavily influence the battery performance. For example, they change the voltage profile, since elemental sulfur can be reformed, prolonging the high voltage plateau^[27] and change the mechanism of precipitation of short order polysulfides avoiding cathode passivation.^[16]

To get an insight into the kinetics of the polysulfide redox reaction we employed impedance spectroscopy. By using the concept of probing the reactivity of lithium polysulfides developed in Ref. [24], the system was first simplified to a symmetrical planar electrode (glassy carbon) cell with a catholyte wetted separator (GC|catholyte|GC). By omitting the magnesium anode, this eliminated any spurious effects of (i) anode impedance contributions and (ii) unwanted reactions between the polysulfides in solution and Mg anode surface, changing the oxidation state and concentration of the polysulfides.

The measured impedance spectra were similar to those reported for lithium polysulfide systems with a large (several $\text{k}\Omega$) arc at middle frequencies, which varied with time.^[24] This contribution was identified to be the charge transfer reaction of polysulfides on the surface of the carbon electrode. The variation in resistance size was up to a factor of 2 which is indicative of disproportionation reactions. Interestingly, the change was not always unidirectional, with the resistance size oscillating between larger and smaller values (Figure 3a). Due to this drift, the impedance spectra could only be reliably measured down to 10 mHz, which most likely excluded a large part of the diffusional contribution of polysulfide transport through the separator pores at lower frequencies.^[28] Regardless of this frequency limitation, the reactivity parameters could be reliably determined, since the arc's characteristic frequency is significantly higher.

Since data obtained on similar design cells with lithium polysulfide catholyte could be well fitted using a Randles circuit,^[24] we employed the same model with slight modifications in this work (Figure 3b). Namely, the lower frequency limit during fitting was set to 20 mHz, since lower frequency points exhibited larger changes due to the before-mentioned disproportionation effects. Note that the limited frequency range

Figure 3. Impedance response of symmetrical glassy carbon cells with magnesium polysulfide catholyte solutions. a) An example of change of spectra with time due to disproportionation (the first spectrum was measured 1 hour after cell assembly and the time period between the subsequent measurements was 18 hours) for MgS_6 catholyte and b) an example of spectrum fit with a Randles equivalent circuit for MgS_8 catholyte.

meant that the contribution of Warburg impedance was close to zero, so unlike in the case of lithium polysulfides this part of spectra was mainly disregarded. This simplification was further supported through the relatively small magnitude of Warburg impedance in comparison with charge transfer impedance on planar electrodes, as discussed in the continuation. We note that the double layer capacitance describes the capacitive properties of the surface very well, so eventual replacement with a corresponding constant phase element only marginally improves the error of fit.

To obtain a range of values corresponding to different disproportionation conditions, the impedance was followed through the course of 4 days. The spectra with the largest and the smallest impedance magnitudes were selected and fitted (Figure S5), providing a range of reactivity parameters for

different magnesium polysulfides (Table 1). The exchange current density i_0 was calculated according to Equations 1 and 2, where R is the gas constant, T the temperature, n the number of electrons transferred, F the Faraday constant, I_0 the exchange current and A the geometrical surface area of the electrode.

$$R_{CT} = \frac{RT}{nF I_0} = \frac{RT}{nF i_0 A} \quad (1)$$

$$i_0 = \frac{I_0}{A} \quad (2)$$

If taking the lower concentration of species into account, the R_{CT} and i_0 values are in line with the reactivity parameters of lithium polysulfides,^[24] suggesting that the cation has a negligible influence on the polysulfide charge transfer reaction. An observable difference is in the parameter trends as regards the average polysulfide chain length. In the case of the lithium sulfur cell, Li_2S_4 and Li_2S_8 catholytes exhibit similar R_{CT} and i_0 values, while Li_2S_6 has a smaller i_0 (and in turn a larger R_{CT}). With magnesium, the trend is different, with MgS_6 and MgS_8 showing similar values and MgS_4 having faster kinetics. This could be explained by assuming that disproportionation tendencies are dependent upon the electrolyte (salts) employed, which is the largest difference of this system in comparison to the lithium one.

These reactivity parameter values have been determined through measurements on symmetrical cells, but can be applied to full Mg–S battery cells as well. In order to do so, one has to account for unwanted side reactions between the magnesium metal surface and sulfur species in the electrolyte in contact with the anode. In this conversion polysulfide chain length is shortened, so parameters pertaining to more reduced sulfur species than originally added to the cell, are expected. Nevertheless, all the parameters are within the same order of magnitude, which is considered a narrow range. In other words, all the magnesium charge transfer reactions have comparable kinetics and none of them could be identified as a clear rate-limiting step in the multistep reactional mechanism.

Although glassy carbon electrodes provide important information on the basic reaction kinetics of polysulfides, porous carbon electrodes are more relevant for the discussion from the application point of view. In order to investigate the behavior of magnesium polysulfide species in the contact with high surface area porous carbon cathodes, symmetrical cells with carbon electrodes prepared from ENSACO 350G carbon (Imerys) were utilized. The impedance spectra measured in the range of 1 MHz to 0.1 mHz are shown in Figure 4a and b. Besides the resistive intercept due to the electrolyte resistance, the essential

Table 1. Essential reactivity parameters of different magnesium polysulfide catholytes (0.018 M concentration in 0.4 M $\text{Mg}(\text{TFSI})_2$ 0.4 M MgCl_2 TEGDME:DOL 1:1 (v:v) electrolyte) given in ranges due to disproportionation drift.

	MgS_8	MgS_6	MgS_4
R_{CT} [$\text{k}\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$]	136–216	112–204	38–66
i_0 [A m^{-2}]	0.0019–0.0011	0.0023–0.0013	0.0068–0.0039
C_{dl} [F]	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Figure 4. Impedance spectra of symmetrical porous carbon cells using magnesium polysulfide catholyte: a) EIS measurements with different polysulfide chain length, b) magnification of high frequency range of (a), c) an example of a simulation of such spectra with a transmission line model, d) magnification of high frequency range of (c), e) explanation of low frequency impedance spectra contributions, f) explanation of high frequency impedance spectra contributions.

features of the spectra constitute a small middle frequency arc (peak frequency below 1 Hz) and a larger low frequency contribution (peak frequency of 0.5 mHz).

For further analysis of the spectra, we used a transmission line model adopted from the reference.^[28] The simulations of the impedance spectra are shown in Figure 4c and d. The model captures all the essential impedance features (both frequencies and sizes) with small deviations at the lowest frequencies, which we attribute to the disproportionation drift. Furthermore, it provides the information on the origin of the contributions (Figure 4e, f). To elaborate the spectra in further detail, the high frequency arc is mainly due to the charge transfer reaction of polysulfide species on the carbon electrode

(the contribution is small due to high electrode surface area) and the low frequency arc mainly due to the diffusion of polysulfides through the separator. Since the values of the diffusional contribution are on the size order of 0.5–3.5 k Ω , this further supports the hypothesis that only reactional parameters could be obtained from the experiment with GC||GC symmetrical cells. Namely in the planar electrode configuration the charge transfer contribution prevails as it is several orders of magnitude larger.

If we examine the peak frequencies of the charge transfer contribution, a slight difference is evident in cells of different design (glassy carbon vs. porous), which are attributed to a change in disproportionation trends due to interaction of polysulfides with porous carbon surface functional groups. Note that, although the peak frequencies of the charge transfer contribution differ between different magnesium polysulfides, the low frequency arc in all cases exhibits the same peak frequency of 0.5 mHz. As explained in Ref. [28], this impedance contribution attributed to the diffusion of species through the separator “feels” the chemical capacitance of an otherwise masked arc for the diffusion of polysulfide species inside the carbon electrode pores. However, in the present specific case the chemical capacitance due to mobile species in separator, C_{ch2} , is significantly higher than that for the diffusion in carbon electrode, C_{ch1} , so the separator contribution prevails. Thus, a similar peak frequency for different polysulfides is indicative of similarity of the respective diffusion coefficients which is rather unexpected.

The scheme of the model employed in Figure 4c and d is shown in Figure S6, while the parameters used in the simulation of the spectra are summarized in Table S1. The components of the transmission line model have a direct physical meaning and can therefore be used for the calculation of certain essential properties of the electrochemical cells.

Chemical diffusion coefficient (D_{chem}) in the separator was calculated according to Equations 3 and 4 with the value of L being the thickness of the separator (260 μm). For the calculation of the transference number of the polysulfides (T_{MgSx}), Equation 5 was used, while the conductivity (λ) of the electrolyte was calculated according to Equations 6 and 7, where A is the geometrical surface area of the electrodes (2 cm^2). The values of the calculated parameters are shown in Table 2.

$$D_{chem} = \frac{L^2}{R_{ser} C_{ch2}} \quad (3)$$

$$R_{ser} = R_{active2} + R_{supp2} \quad (4)$$

Table 2. Essential transport parameters of different magnesium polysulfide catholytes (0.018 M concentration in 0.4 M Mg(TFSI)₂ 0.4 M MgCl₂ TEGDME:DOL 1:1 (v:v) electrolyte).

	MgS ₈	MgS ₆	MgS ₄
D_{chem} [m^2s^{-1}]	$9.33 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$9.39 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$9.43 \cdot 10^{-11}$
T_{MgSx}	0.0129	0.0065	0.0026
λ [S cm^{-1}]	$1.55 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.54 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.53 \cdot 10^{-3}$

$$T_{\text{MgS}_x} = \frac{R_{\text{supp}2}}{R_{\text{active}2} + R_{\text{supp}2}} \quad (5)$$

$$A = \frac{L}{R_{\text{parallel}}A} \quad (6)$$

$$R_{\text{parallel}} = \frac{R_{\text{active}2}R_{\text{supp}2}}{R_{\text{active}2} + R_{\text{supp}2}} \quad (7)$$

The values for the chemical diffusion coefficient are surprisingly similar, as already indicated by the similarity of the peak frequencies mentioned above. In fact, within the experimental error, we might conclude that the values of diffusion coefficients are more or less the same. The polysulfide transference numbers are all very low, since the concentration of magnesium polysulfides in the supporting electrolyte was low (0.018 M) and most of the charge is carried through the migration of 0.4 M Mg(TFSI)₂ and 0.4 M MgCl₂ supporting salts in the electrolyte. From this, the similarity of the electrolyte conductivity is also explained.

In order to test more concentrated electrolytes, which would be obtained in lean electrolyte/sulfur ratio (a necessary requirement for obtaining a higher energy density Mg–S cells), higher concentrations of MgS₈ were added to the electrolyte solution (the electrolyte loading of 20 μL or 10 μL per mg of sulfur in the cathode, would result in 0.2 M and 0.4 M MgS₈ solutions, although even higher concentrations are expected locally in the carbon cathode pores). Interestingly, in the more concentrated catholyte solutions (0.05 M, 0.1 M), we detected a white precipitate (Figure 5). The color of the solid suggests that, most likely, the magnesium salt(s) used for electrolyte preparation precipitate(s). If we further consider the solubility product equations (Equations 8–10), we see that both Mg(TFSI)₂ and MgCl₂ could precipitate if the concentration of Mg²⁺ ions is increased by the addition of MgS₈. However, without obtaining the specific values of solubility products (furthermore, we most likely have a formation of complex species which have their own solubility product), we cannot predict which one is more probable to precipitate.

Figure 5. a) Photograph of solutions of different concentrations of MgS₈ in 0.4 M Mg(TFSI)₂ / 0.4 M MgCl₂ TEGDME:DOL 1:1 (v:v) electrolyte; b) white precipitate formed in the most concentrated polysulfide solution.

The precipitate was isolated and analyzed with IR and XRD (Figure S7), which confirmed that the precipitate has no characteristic peaks/bands of polysulfides, although it was also proven it was neither pure Mg(TFSI)₂ or pure MgCl₂ (for details see the Supporting information). Since it is known that Mg(TFSI)₂ and MgCl₂ form complexes^[29] in such already concentrated electrolytes, we assume that some form of co-precipitation of the complex mixture takes place.

Interestingly, high salt concentrations in the electrolyte (“solvent-in-salt electrolytes”) are a widely suggested approach in Li–S batteries for decreasing the solubility and dissolution of polysulfide species and in turn improving battery cell performance.^[30] Our results suggest such an approach is not possible for any chosen electrolyte system, since polysulfides and salt anions compete for solvation. This is an important distinction and a crucial drawback, since it means that the same approach of increasing the extent of sulfur conversion as described in the lithium-sulfur battery case cannot be employed in the magnesium-sulfur battery cells. In this case, the specific interactions therefore resulted in an undesired precipitation of electrolyte salt and dissolution of polysulfides. This phenomenon should not be disregarded, as electrolyte salt precipitation during Mg–S battery cell discharge would likely signify detrimental consequences for the cell performance. Namely, severe performance and material degradation is expected if such supporting salt precipitation takes place during battery cell operation.

3. Conclusions

Magnesium polysulfides were synthesized in the form of *N*-Melm complexes and its structure was confirmed with sulfur K-edge XANES spectra, ¹H NMR and ATR-IR spectroscopy. UV-Vis spectroscopy was used to prove their tendencies to disproportionate in electrolyte and impedance spectroscopy to probe their reactivity and diffusivity. By evaluation and fitting of impedance spectra of simplified glassy carbon cells in contact with magnesium polysulfide catholytes we determined their reactivity and transport parameters (exchange current densities, chemical diffusion coefficient, transference numbers and conductivities), data essential to advance computational efforts on modelling of magnesium-sulfur batteries. The impedance spectroscopy results on porous carbon electrodes also provide information on the bottle-neck

processes during their operation, which is the diffusion of polysulfide species from the bulk of the electrolyte in the separator towards the electrode surface.

We show that high polysulfide concentration catholytes could not be prepared in the studied system, since the electrolyte salt(s) precipitate(s) upon the addition of magnesium polysulfides. This suggests important implications for Mg–S battery cell performance (proven when employing electrolyte based on Mg(TFSI)₂/MgCl₂ mixture of salts, but possible in other electrolyte systems as well). Results obtained in this work point out the need for a careful electrolyte design for Mg–S batteries, especially if the strategy of high concentration electrolytes is applied as a potential solution for reducing solubility and mitigation of polysulfide shuttle.

Experimental Section

Materials

All the chemicals and the preparation of cells were done inside an Ar-filled MBraun glovebox (O₂ < 1.0 ppm, H₂O < 1.0 ppm). The magnesium salts, Mg(TFSI)₂ (from Solvionic, 99.5%) was dried at 225 °C for 3 days under vacuum, MgCl₂ (ultradry, Alfa Aesar, 99.99% metal trace) was used as received. Solvents (tetraethylene glycol dimethyl ether (TEGDME), 1,3-dioxolane (DOL)) were dried in a multistep process using Al₂O₃, molecular sieves, and distillation, after which the water content was measured by Karl Fischer titration (Mettler Toledo, C20) and kept below 2 ppm. Glassy carbon electrodes were purchased as 2 cm² discs from HTW, Germany and used as received. Porous carbon electrodes were prepared by mixing ENSACO 360G carbon (Imerys) with PVdF (Sigma-Aldrich) in 9:1 ratio, preparing a suspension in NMP (Merck) and casting in on a carbon coated Al foil with doctor Blade applicator. After drying at 50 °C over night, 2 cm² electrodes measuring 10 μm in thickness were punched out of the prepared sheet. Cells were prepared by stacking the electrodes and glass fiber separator (GF–A, Whatman, 260 μm), wetting it with 100 μL (GC symmetrical cells) or 150 μL (porous symmetrical cells) and sealing it in a Triplex pouch cell prepared beforehand with Ni contacts.

Synthesis

Magnesium polysulfides were synthesized as Mg[N-Melm]_xS_y, where x is 8, 6 and 4, complexes according to the literature.^[20,21] Briefly, the Mg powder and sulfur were mixed in different stoichiometric ratios in *N*-methylimidazole (*N*-Melm) at 100 °C for 12 h. The solution was left to cool down and it was filtrated. The products were crystalized by adding toluene.

IR Spectroscopy

The ATR-IR spectra were measured inside an Ar filled glovebox on a Bruker Alpha II equipped with a diamond ATR crystal with 128 scans and 4 cm⁻¹ resolution from 4000–400 cm⁻¹.

X-ray Absorption

Sulfur K-edge XANES measurements were performed at the XAFS beamline of synchrotron Elettra (Basovizza, Trieste) in fluorescence-detection mode.^[31] Experimental details were the same as explained elsewhere.^[23,32]

UV/Vis Spectroscopy

UV-vis spectra were measured every 10 minutes in the range of 400–800 nm on a PerkinElmer Lambda 950 UV-vis spectrometer. For the measurement glass fiber separator GF-D (Whatman, 670 μm) was wetted with 200 μL of the polysulfide catholyte and sealed inside a Triplex pouch cells with quartz glass window.^[33,34] For reference, an electrolyte wetted separator was used.

Electrochemistry

Impedance spectra were measured on VMP-3 potentiostat/galvanostat (Bio-Logic) at OCV in the range of 1 MHz–10 mHz (GC symmetrical cells) or 1 MHz–0.1 mHz (porous symmetrical cells) with 10 mV amplitude (rms).

Impedance Spectra Fitting and Simulation

Fitting of impedance spectra with the Randles circuit was done in EC-Lab V 11.10. Simulation of impedance spectra with the transmission line model were carried out using a self-written code in Python 3 with standard scientific packages (NumPy and Matplotlib) as reported elsewhere.^[28]

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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